

KINETICS AND MECHANISM OF RACEMISATION OF OPTICALLY ACTIVE COBALTIC TRISBIGUANIDE COMPLEX

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The velocity of racemisation of *l*- and *d*-cobaltic trisbiguanidinium chloro-*d*-tartrate, as well as of the pure optical enantiomers, *l*- and *d*-cobaltic trisbiguanidinium chloride, in aqueous solution have been determined at different temperatures. The activation energy in each case has been computed from the temperature coefficient of the velocity constant of inversion with the help of Arrhenius's equation. In the case of the pure enantiomers the value for the Arrhenius's constant (PZ) was found to be very low from the point of view of the unimolecular type of change. Addition of many simple and complex foreign cations, including H-ion, has been found to retard catalytically the velocity of racemisation of the active cobaltic trisbiguanidinium chloride. Ca^{++} , Cu^{++} , Mn^{++} and H^+ are most effective in this respect and almost completely inhibit the change even when present in very small quantities. The change is, however, unaffected by anions excepting the OH^- -ion, which exercises, on the other hand, a strong accelerating effect upon the velocity of racemisation. The existing views regarding the mechanism of racemisation have been discussed in the light of experimental results described in this paper, as well as of those previously recorded by others. A new mechanism of the phenomenon of racemisation has been suggested on the basis of intramolecular rearrangement.

The phenomenon of racemisation of optically active co-ordination compounds has lately become a subject of special interest for investigation. The mechanism of racemisation implies that of inversion till the two optically active antipodes are present in equal amounts in dynamic equilibrium. Two main views have been advanced relating to this phenomenon. The one, due to Werner (*Ber.*, 1912, 45, 3061), is based on the *intramolecular rearrangement* of the co-ordinated bidentate groups. Thus in the case of active potassium cobalti- or chromioxalate none of the three oxalato groups are entirely detached from the central atom, only one of them vacates momentarily one of its two co-ordination positions in the molecule remaining bound at the other position, and before it can rejoin a rearrangement with one of the other oxalate groups occurs, leading to the formation of its enantiomorph (Fig. 1a and c).

FIG. 1

Thomas (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 1140), on the other hand, considers *secondary ionisation* as the cause of racemisation. He assumes that potassium chromi- or cobaltioxalate, for instance, in aqueous solution suffers partial dissociation, as shown below, giving rise to a planar complex,

Subsequent recombination leads to racemisation, due to equal probability for the formation of both the enantiomers.

Thomas's view has been criticised by Johnson and co-workers (Johnson, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1935, 31, 1615; Beese and Johnson, *ibid.*, 1635; Bushra and Johnson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 1941), who could not detect the presence of any free (C_2O_4) -ion in the solution of chromi- or cobaltioxalate, nor did they observe any reduction in the rate of racemisation of these active substances by the addition of potassium oxalate (common ion effect). Furthermore, both chromioxalate and cobaltioxalate have been found to racemise even in the crystalline state (Johnson and Mead, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1935, 31, 1621; Johnson, *ibid.*, 1620). Finally Long (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 61, 570) has failed to detect any exchange between oxalate ion containing a radioactive isotope of carbon with chromioxalate at 35°.

Johnson and collaborators are, therefore, in favour of the alternative view of racemisation through intramolecular rearrangement, due to an interchange of two points of attachment in *cis*-positions (Fig. 1a and c). But they at the same time assume further that water molecules, from the solvent or water of crystallisation, possibly participate in the process (*cf.* Charonnat, *Ann. Chim.*, 1931, 16, 150); for, they have observed that hydrated potassium chromioxalate racemises faster at room temperature than at 115°, while its strychnine salt (also hydrated) does not racemise at ordinary temperature, but racemisation occurs on heating as well as at the room temperature in the anhydrous state (dried over P_2O_5). These authors have also studied the kinetics of racemisation of $[Cr(C_2O_4)_3]^{3-}$, $[Co(C_2O_4)_3]^{3-}$ and $[Cr.en(C_2O_4)_2]^-$ in aqueous solution, and, in addition, the catalytic (accelerating) influence of foreign ions upon the velocity of their inversion (*en* = ethylenediamine).

These oxalato-complexes in aqueous solution are thermodynamically and otherwise rather unstable, and cobaltioxalate is moreover known to be highly sensitive to light. It was, therefore, expected that the study of an energetically stable, but optically unstable, compound might furnish more useful information on the subject. A suitable substance with these properties has been found in cobaltic trisbiguanidinium chloride, whose resolution and optical properties have been described in our previous paper (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 18, 289). A study of the velocity of racemisation in aqueous solution of the diastereoisomerides—the chloro-*d*-tartrates of the *d*- and the *l*-complex, as well as of the complex enantiomers, *d*- and *l*- $[Co(BigH^+)_3]Cl_3$, at various temperatures and in the presence of a number of foreign ions is presented in this paper. From a consideration of the results obtained, the nature of the mechanism of racemisation has been discussed at the end.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The complex trisbiguanidinium ion, $[Co(BigH^+)_3]^{3+}$, where $BigH = C_2N_3H_7$ (biguanide), in aqueous solution is quite stable. A solution of the complex chloride can be heated to boiling without any appreciable permanent change. This does not, of course, exclude any hydrolytic equilibrium in solution on heating. In fact, evidence for such equilibrium has been discussed hereafter. Its optically active components in the solid state retain their activity unchanged even after a year; in solution their activity suffers no change at room temperature (25°) for over 24 hours. The crystals of the diastereoisomerides as well as of the active chlorides can be heated to 105° without any loss of their activity; the hydrated crystals of the former, however, became anhydrous at 62° (*cf.* Ray and Dutt, *loc. cit.*).

All measurements of rotation were made with aqueous solutions of the active salts in a Schmidt and Haensch's polarimeter provided with an electrically controlled thermostat ($\pm 1^\circ$), using a sodium vapour lamp as the light source. The velocity constant of inversion for the active complex ion is deduced from the equation, $dx/dt = k(a-x) - kx = k(a-2x)$,

where a = initial concentration of the active salt, x = concentration of its optical antipode formed by inversion after a time t , and k = velocity constant of inversion of the active forms. Hence,

$$k = \frac{2.303}{2t} \log_{10} \frac{R_0}{R_t} \quad \text{and} \quad T \text{ (half-life)} = \frac{2.303}{2k} \log_{10} 2; \quad \text{where } R_0 = \text{initial rotation, } R_t =$$

rotation after a time t in minutes. From a number of pairs of polarimeter readings at each temperature the values for the unimolecular velocity constant of inversion were calculated and k represents the mean of several such closely agreeing values. No anomaly in the k -value was observed during the entire course of the experiments, which usually lasted for several hours and sometimes even for days, unlike those found by Johnson and co-workers for chromioxalates.

Of the two diastereoisomerides, l - and d -trisbiguanidinium chloro- d -tartrate, the l -modification can be obtained easily in a quite pure state (*cf.* R&y and Dutt, *loc. cit.*). This was, therefore, employed for measuring their rates of racemisation, specially in view of the fact, described hereafter, that the presence of small quantities of foreign ions exerts a pronounced catalytic effect upon the racemisation velocity.

The unimolecular velocity constant k_1 and k_2 for the l - and the d -diastereoisomerides respectively were calculated from

$$k_1 + k_2 = \frac{2.303}{t} \log_{10} \frac{K}{K - (K+1) \frac{x}{a}} \quad \dots = \frac{2.303 \log_{10} \frac{K}{K - (K+1) \frac{R_0 - R_t}{2R_0}}}{t}$$

where K = equilibrium constant for the two diastereoisomerides = k_1/k_2 and a , x , t , R_0 and R_t denote values as already stated.

The value of K for 45° is 1.049 and the values for other temperatures were computed from the heat of reaction 923 calories involved in the transformation of l - into d -form (*cf.* R&y and Dutt, *loc. cit.*).

The Velocity Constant of Inversion of the Diastereoisomerides

l - and d -[Co(BigH⁺)₃]^{Cl} d -C₁₂H₄O₆ and their Temperature Coefficients

The preparation and the properties of the diastereoisomerides have been described in our previous paper. All measurements were made with 1% solution in a 10 cm. tube; the rotations α_0 , the velocity constants and the half-life period, T , are shown in Table I.

It will be observed, as could be expected from the variation of equilibrium constant with temperature (R&y and Dutt, *loc. cit.*), that the velocity constants of the two diastereoisomerides approach each other closely with rise of temperature and become practically identical above 56° . The partial racemate at about this temperature will consequently consist of 50:50 mixture of the two active forms. The phenomenon of asymmetric transformation described in our previous paper cannot, therefore, occur here.

TABLE I

t (min.)	0	1020	1500	2460	Temp. = 46.1°	$k_1 \times 10^4$	$k_2 \times 10^4$	T_1 (hrs.)	T_2 (hrs.)
a_D (deg.)	3.35	2.20	1.80	1.20		2.052	1.955	28.15	29.55
t	0	240	480	1440	Temp. = 50.2°	3.011	2.912	19.07	19.65
a_D	3.35	2.90	2.50	1.38					
t	0	180	120	1380	Temp. = 51.2°	1.500	1.500	12.00	12.60
a_D	3.35	1.84	2.28	0.95					
t	0	180	420	1380	Temp. = 56.1°	5.630	5.610	10.17	10.30
a_D	3.35	2.73	2.09	0.71					

By plotting the values of $\log_{10} k_1$ and $\log_{10} k_2$ against the reciprocal of absolute temperatures

Fig. 2

(Fig. 2, curves 1 and 2), the activation energy of the two modifications were calculated with the application of Arrhenius's equation, $k = s e^{-E/RT}$. The values found for E_1 and E_2 are 21,350 cal. and 22,310 cal. respectively. The straight lines representing the relationship between $\log k_1$ and $\log k_2$ with temperature seem to cross each other at 56°. The solution in equilibrium at any temperature above 56° will, therefore, show a residual *laevo* rotation. Unfortunately, however, the complex ion in solution gives indication of incipient hydrolysis on keeping for about an hour at 61°, or for several hours at 59° (*vide*

infra), rendering any prolonged measurements for equilibrium beyond 56° of little value.

The difference between E_1 and E_2 , 22,310 - 21,350 = 960 cal. is the heat evolved in the transformation of the *l*- into *d*-form, which agrees fairly well with the value of 923 cal., previously determined from equilibrium consideration (Ray and Dutt, *loc. cit.*). The values for Arrhenius's constant, $s = PZ$, calculated from the activation energy figures, are $10^{8.14}$ and $10^{8.8}$ for the *l*- and the *d*-variety respectively, when the velocity constants are expressed in reciprocal seconds.

Velocity Constants of Inversion of *l*- and *d*-[Co(BigH')₂] Cl₂ and their Temperature Coefficients

The preparation of the pure enantiomers has been described in our previous paper (*loc. cit.*). Most of the measurements in this paper were carried out with the *l*-isomer, which is more easily prepared.

The velocity constants for *l*-complex measured for different concentrations at 46.1°, are given in Table II.

TABLE II

Conc (mols/litre) $\times 10^3$	...	10.67	21.34	42.71	63.76	85.25
$k \times 10^4$	...	2.46	2.57	2.49	2.46	2.50
„ (mean)	...	2.48				

For the dextro-isomeride at the same temperature for a concentration, $c \times 10^3 = 42.68$, the value of $k \times 10^4$ was found to be 2.46.

The results show that, within the limits of the concentration employed, the transformation is strictly of the unimolecular type.

For the measurement of temperature coefficient a 3% solution of the *l*.-iso-salt in 2 cm. tubes was used. The results are summarised in Table III.

TABLE III

Temp.	...	39.5	44.1	46.1	48.1	50.7	52.7	54.8	57.1	59.2
$k \times 10^4$	...	1.52	2.14	2.46	2.82	3.24	3.72	4.28	4.94	5.84
T (hours)	...	38.2	27.0	23.5	20.5	17.8	15.5	13.5	11.7	10.3

Calculated from the slope of the $\log_{10} k - T^{-1}$ curve (Fig. 2, curve 3) with the help of Arrhenius's equation the activation energy E equals 13,930 cal. and $\log_{10} PZ$ equals 4.16 on the basis of k expressed in sec^{-1} . As reflected in its lower activation energy the temperature coefficient of increase of the inversion constant of the active $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)_2\text{Cl}_2]$ is smaller than that of its diastereoisomerides, though the magnitude of the k -value for the former at lower temperatures is actually higher (e.g. at 46.1° these are 2.46, 2.052 and 1.955 resp.). The situation is, however, reversed at somewhat higher temperatures. In view of the lower activation energy of the active complex chloride, compared with those of its diastereoisomerides, a much higher value for its rate of racemisation than actually observed might have been expected. This is obviously offset by a rather abnormally low value of PZ . Similar low PZ -values have also been reported for the active anion $[\text{Cr}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_3]^{3-}$ by Bushra and Johnson (*loc. cit.*); $\log_{10} PZ$ for which should be 6.2 in place of 8.05 when k is expressed in sec^{-1} . An increase of activation energy for the diastereoisomerides is accompanied by an increase of PZ -values. A similar relation has been observed by Fairclough and Hinshelwood for some bimolecular reactions (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 538). The theoretical interpretation of such relationship has been discussed by Hinshelwood (*ibid.*, 1935, 1114). But the value of 4.16 in the present case is rather unusually low for a unimolecular reaction. It may, therefore, be suggested that the water molecules as solvent are possibly not inert, but exercise their influence by modifying the rate of activation and deactivation, or by altering the number of internal degrees of freedom of the molecule (*cf.* Moelwyn Hughes, "The Kinetics of Reactions in Solutions," 1933, p. 158). The former is rather improbable for a complicated molecule like the present one, and the latter contributes only to the energy of activation. It is more likely, however, that the low value of PZ , or rather of the probability factor P , is due to an unusual delay in the specific energy transfer, which means an increase in the time-interval between *pre-activation* and *critical activation*, with the result that most of the activated molecules suffer deactivation before the transformation sets in.

At 59.2°, after a period of 12-14 hours it was found that the k -value went on increasing. After 24 hours it became 7.23×10^{-4} . At 61° this abnormal behaviour of the solution was more pronounced, as is evident from the following α_D - and k -values of a 2% solution of the active salt in a 2 cm. tube (Table IV).

TABLE IV

t (min.)	...	0	60	180	360
α_D	...	1.81	1.65	1.34	0.70
$k \times 10^4$	...		7.70	8.35	13.20

The solution had a p_H of 8.45 to begin with, which changed to 6.52 after the experiment. A hydrolytic reaction leading to the formation of a hydroxo-aquo complex as in the case of the corresponding chromium compound (Rây and Saha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 15, 353; Rây and Ghosh, *ibid.*, 1942, 19, 1) possibly becomes prominent at this temperature.

Influence of Foreign Ions on the Velocity of Racemisation

A. Cations

The higher values of activation energy of the diastereoisomerides seem to suggest their greater stability compared to that of the active complex chlorides. That combination with an active optically stable ion of opposite character imparts greater stability to an active optically unstable ion, is a phenomenon of general occurrence. This, along with the observation that unimolecular reactions are usually sensitive to homogeneous catalysis, led us to study the influence of foreign ions on the velocity of racemisation of active $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)_2]\text{Cl}_2$. Johnson and co-workers (*loc. cit.*) have already observed an accelerating effect of cations on the racemisation velocity of $[\text{Cr}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_3]^{3-}$, $[\text{Cr en}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_2]^-$ and $[\text{Co}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_2]^{2-}$. Our results, on the contrary, show a catalytic retardation in all cases excepting that of OH-ion. The experimental results are summarised in the following tables. All measurements were made at 46.1° with 2% (4.3×10^{-2} mols/litre) solution of the *l*-hydrochloride in 2 cm. tubes.

TABLE V
Catalyst—H-ion (HCl)

Conc. of catalyst (mols./litre).	$k \times 10^5$.	Conc. of catalyst (mols./litre).	$k \times 10^5$
1×10^{-1}	Decomposes	2.5×10^{-4}	4.04
5×10^{-2}	2890	1.0×10^{-4}	No change for over 27 hrs.
1×10^{-2}	545	0.8×10^{-4}	11.80
1×10^{-3}	206	0.7×10^{-4}	16.40
6.7×10^{-4}	24.90	0.625×10^{-4}	18.80
5×10^{-4}	15.70	0.5×10^{-4}	24.60

The results are represented graphically by plotting the logarithm of the concentration against $\log_{10} k$ in Fig. 3.

From an examination of Table V and Fig. 3, it will be observed that the catalytic effect of H-ion varies according to its concentration apparently in an irregular manner. At 0.5×10^{-4} molar, no catalytic effect is noticeable, beyond this up to a concentration of 0.8×10^{-4} molar the k -value continually diminishes, this retardation effect reaches its maximum at 1×10^{-4} molar when the rotation of the solution was found to remain unchanged for over 27 hours. The substance can thus be optically stabilised in solution at 46.1° with this concentration of H-ion. This is rather significant and somewhat unique. With further increase in the H-ion concentration the solution loses its stability with gradual increase in the rate of its racemisation till at about 6.7×10^{-4} molar it regains its normal uncatalysed value. But the increase in the specific inversion rate continues till at 1×10^{-3} molar of H-ion there occurs a sharp break in the curve. Beyond 5×10^{-3} molar of H-ion the substance suffers decomposition by the acid. Even at 0.05 and 0.01

molar H-ion concentration k -values were unreliable for readings after half an hour. The values relating to these concentrations, given in the table, correspond to readings before any decomposition sets in:

Fig. 3

FIG. 4

If the difference between the normal uncatalysed velocity constant k_0 , and the observed catalysed value k_{obs} , be plotted against concentration, a straight line is obtained for the concentration range where the catalytic effect is negative. This is shown in Fig. 4 with $\text{log}_{10}(k_0 - k_{\text{obs}})$ plotted against $\text{log}_{10}c$. Such straight line relationship cannot, however, be found for the remaining higher concentrations where the net effect is one of acceleration. Obviously, therefore, above the concentration of 1×10^{-4} molar, two effects are superimposed—an additional accelerating influence besides the characteristic catalytic retardation. This acceleration is presumably associated with some partial and gradual change in the composition of the complex ion itself by the acid. This change may reasonably be attributed to the gradual formation of optically inactive *trans*-hydroxo-aquo-bisbiguanide and diaquo-bisbiguanide complexes. Evidences for the formation of the first type have already been referred to (*vide supra*). The latter is likely to be formed at a comparatively increased concentration of HCl as all hydroxo-compounds tend to change into aquo-complexes in the presence of acids as shown below.

It is more likely that both are formed and exist in equilibrium at all concentrations of the acid beyond 1×10^{-4} molar (*cf.* the ascending portions of the curve, Fig. 3), the proportion of the diaquo-complex increasing with the acid concentration.

An analysis of the k -values, observed in the presence of various metallic ions (simple and complex) and recorded in Table VI may be made here.

The catalytic retardation due to univalent simple ions is considerably smaller than those of the polyvalent ones. Among themselves, Tl^+ is most effective and differs in this respect from the alkali metal and ammonium ions. This may be traced to the difference in the electronic structure

TABLE VI

Catalyst—metallic ions

(1) Univalent

Salt.	Conc. (mols./litre).	$k \times 10^4$.	Salt.	Conc. (mols./litre).	$k \times 10^4$.
LiCl	1×10^{-1}	10'40	KCl	0.5×10^{-1}	17'90
NH_4Cl	"	11'80	"	"	18'0 (d)
NaCl	"	18'30	RbCl	1×10^{-1}	9'63
"	0.5×10^{-1}	20'50	CsCl	"	8'55
KCl	1×10^{-1}	14'50	TlCl	1×10^{-1}	9'70

(2) Bivalent

$CaCl_2$	0.5×10^{-1}	—	$BeCl_2$	0.1×10^{-1}	3'60
"	0.5×10^{-2}	—	"	0.5×10^{-2}	9'62
"	0.5×10^{-3}	9'70	$MgCl_2$	0.1×10^{-1}	2'68
$SrCl_2$	0.5×10^{-1}	—	"	0.5×10^{-2}	9'70
"	0.5×10^{-2}	—	$ZnCl_2$	0.5×10^{-2}	5'44
"	0.5×10^{-3}	9'80	$CdCl_2$	"	5'93
$BaCl_2$	0.5×10^{-1}	—	$HgCl_2$	"	3'34
"	0.5×10^{-2}	11'40	$CuCl_2$	"	3'46
"	"	12'20 (d)	$MnCl_2$	"	3'46
$PbCl_2$	"	15'20	$CoCl_2$	"	10'80
			$NiCl_2$	"	11'20

(3) Tervalent

$AlCl_3$	0.1×10^{-2}	5'70
"	0.5×10^{-2}	6'06
$LaCl_3$	0.1×10^{-2}	3'42
"	0.5×10^{-2}	3'95

(4) Quadrivalent

$ZrCl_4$	0.5×10^{-2}	4'26
$ThCl_4$	0.1×10^{-2}	4'28
"	0.5×10^{-2}	5'20

(5) Complex ions

$[Co_2Co(NH_3)_4]Cl$	0.5×10^{-2}	7'55	$[Co(NH_3)_6]Cl_2$	0.5×10^{-1}	8'69
$[(NO_2)_2Co(NH_3)_4]Cl$	"	7'41	$[Co(en)_3]Cl_2$	"	10'20
$[Cu(BigH^+)_2]Cl_2$	"	3'56	$[Cr(en)_3]Cl_3$	"	9'07
$[Ni(BigH^+)_2]Cl_2$	"	3'34	$[Cr(BigH^+)_2]Cl_2$	"	10'10
$[ClCo(NH_3)_4]Cl_2$	"	9'75	$[Co(BigH^+)_2]Cl_2$	"	24'60 (no effect)
			(racemic)		

of Tl^+ ion which, unlike the alkali ions, does not possess an inert gas configuration. The catalytic activity of alkali ions excepting Li^+ follows the order of their ionic radius. Thus, $Cs^+ > Rb^+ > NH_4^+ > K^+ > Na^+$. Li^+ stands between Rb^+ and NH_4^+ in its catalytic power, instead of following Na^+ in order of its ionic volume. Lithium, therefore, differs from its congeners in this as in many other respects, presumably due to the helium like structure of its ion. Tl^+ with a radius of $1.49\text{\AA}$, which is almost equal to that of Rb^+ , is much more powerful than even Cs^+ .

The simple bivalent cations may be divided into four groups:—(i) those having inert gas structure— Be^{++} , Mg^{++} , Ca^{++} , Sr^{++} and Ba^{++} ; (ii) those with an outermost shell of 18 electrons— Zn^{++} , Cd^{++} and Hg^{++} ; (iii) ions with an outermost shell of 2 electrons— Pb^{++} ; and (iv) ions of the first transitional series with variable electrons >8 and <18 in the outermost shell— Mn^{++} , Co^{++} , Ni^{++} and Cu^{++} . The bivalent cations along with the ter- and quadrivalent ones possess very high retarding power. All the cations of group (i) are almost equally active. The values for Be^{++} and Mg^{++} suffer somewhat in their quantitative character due to hydrolysis. At a concentration of 0.5×10^{-3} molar Ca^{++} , Sr^{++} and Ba^{++} practically inhibit racemisation at the experimental temperature, no change of rotation being observed for the solution of the active salt for over 18 hours. Ions of group (ii) are somewhat stronger than those of group (i) in their catalytic power. Of these again Hg^{++} appears to be the most active. This is rather striking in view of the fact that $HgCl_2$ is a very weak electrolyte. At the high dilution employed, however, it might suffer considerable dissociation into ions. Among the ions of the transitional series Cu^{++} and Mn^{++} are as powerful inhibitors as mercury. Co^{++} and Ni^{++} , on the other hand, approach Sr^{++} and Ba^{++} in their catalytic effect. Pb^{++} , the only member of group (iii), is somewhat less active than Ni^{++} .

The ter- and quadrivalent ions that have been examined, with the exception of Al^{3+} , are slightly more active than Zn^{++} and Cd^{++} . The effect of hydrolysis of the catalyst in all these cases obscures the results to a certain extent.

Among the complex ions that have been examined, those with octahedral configuration are comparatively less active than those with planar configuration. These latter, namely copper and nickel complexes, resemble the simple Cu^{++} , Mn^{++} and Hg^{++} ions in their power of catalytic retardation. The univalent octahedral complexes are again somewhat more effective than the bi- and trivalent ones. The latter approach the simple Co^{++} ion in this respect.

A few measurements were made to study the catalytic racemisation also of the $d-[Co(BigH^+)_2]Cl_2$. The results are practically identical with those observed for its l -enantiomer. These are indicated by the letter d against the k -value in Table VI.

All the simple salts used as catalysts in these experiments were of guaranteed purity (Kahlbaum's *pro analysi*). The complex salts were all freshly prepared in a pure state in our laboratory.

B. Anions

No appreciable catalytic activity due to anions was observed with the single exception of OH^- ion, which, on the other hand, was found to accelerate enormously the rate of racemisation (Table VII).

The action of $NaOH$ is rather irregular. Judging from the acceleration effect induced by $[Co(BigH^+)_2](OH)_2$, that due to $NaOH$ in the first two cases is too small to fit in with the high OH^- ion concentration of the solution. The retardation effect of the Na^+ is alone insufficient to account for this low value, as its catalytic activity at the concentration employed is of little signi-

ficance. Some chemical interaction between NaOH and the reactant, besides the simple double decomposition, is likely to complicate the issue. To a certain extent this is indicated by a diminution of about 0.3 to 0.4 units in the p_H -value of the solution after a few hours or at the end of the experiment.

TABLE VII

Substance.	Conc. (mols./litre).	p_H (H-electrode).	Conc. of OH ⁻ (mols./litre)	$k \times 10^6$.
[Co(BigH ⁺) ₂](OH) ₂	0.5×10^{-3}	8.85	0.71×10^{-5}	542
"	0.375×10^{-3}	8.70	0.50×10^{-5}	496
"	0.25×10^{-3}	8.50	0.32×10^{-5}	448
NaOH	—	10.35	0.224×10^{-3}	32.5
"	—	10.95	0.89×10^{-3}	165
"	—	11.40	0.25×10^{-3}	220

Other anions

TABLE VIII

Conc. (mols./litre) = 0.5×10^{-3} .

Salt	...	...	KCl	KBr	KI	KNO ₃
$k \times 10^6$	...	...	23.3	22.8	22.8	22.8

The small retardation is due to K⁺ only. Bivalent anions like SO₄²⁻, CO₃²⁻, etc., could not be used as they form precipitates with the complex ion.

The Concentration of the Catalyst and the Magnitude of Retardation

It has already been shown that in the case of H-ion there is a direct linear relationship between the magnitude of retardation and the concentration of the catalyst within a certain range.

FIG. 5

A few experiments were, therefore, carried out to investigate if similar relationship also obtains in the case of other cations, specially the most potent ones, namely, Ca^{++} , Mn^{++} and Cu^{++} . The results are summarised in Table IX and represented graphically in Fig. 5. All measurements were made at 46.1° with a 2% (4.3×10^{-2} molar) solution of $l\text{-}[\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)_3]\text{Cl}_2$. Two series of measurements were made at each concentration and the k -values given represent the mean of closely agreeing values of the two series.

Plotting the values of $\log_{10} r$ against those of $\log_{10}(k_0 - k_{\text{obs}})$, no linear relationship could, however, be obtained.

Whether the catalyst acts by lowering the PZ -value, or increasing the activation energy of the molecule, or by affecting both, cannot be discussed for the present, unless a systematic investigation of the temperature coefficient of the catalysed racemisation for each catalyst is taken up.

TABLE IX

Conc. (mols./litre) $\times 10^4$...	5.0	2.50	1.25	0.625	0.3125
$k \times 10^6$ CaCl_2 ...	9.70	12.60	16.50	20.60	24.90
" MnCl_2 ...	3.46	7.79	13.70	19.40	24.40
" CuCl_2 ...	3.46	6.26	13.0	18.50	24.20

Mechanism of Racemisation

Johnson and co-workers have, as already mentioned, shown that Thomas's theory of inversion, based on the assumption of secondary ionisation, cannot be supported, since the validity of his experimental evidences are open to serious question. The alternative view of an intramolecular rearrangement, due to Werner, has been advocated by them with an additional assumption of participation by the solvent. But before an interchange of two points of attachment in *cis*-positions necessary for such rearrangement can occur, there must be at least a momentary rupture of the chemical bonds at those positions, even though none of the chelate groups or molecules are completely detached from the central atom. This obviously involves the possibility of chemical decomposition during inversion even under conditions where the molecule is thermodynamically stable. Since all the six bonds in an octahedral complex are equivalent being of d^2sp^3 hybrid type, there is no reason why two such bonds attached to one and the same chelate group will not suffer similar rupture at the same time. There is, however, no experimental evidence of chemical decomposition being invariably associated with inversion. The suggestion, that such an interchange without any rupture of the chemical bond is possible if the bonds concerned move, along with the attached groups, towards each other, pass across and then interchange their position, is also untenable because of considerable steric hindrance involved in the mechanism.

A more probable hypothesis regarding the mechanism of racemisation may be based upon the following picture.

The free individual existence of the two enantiomers in the pure state, in spite of their having identical energy content, indicates that there is a potential barrier between them. Hence the supply of some activation energy is necessary for their interconversion. Addition of energy to a molecule leads to an increase in its translational, rotational and vibrational motions, and the molecule is said to be activated or excited. A molecule with a regular, octahedral configuration in its normal state, when excited with sufficient quanta of energy, may lose this configuration and assume another which is stable under the new conditions. On the subsequent removal of

excess energy, the molecule returns again to its normal octahedral configuration, and since both *d*- and *l*-forms are endowed with equal energy content, there is equal probability for the formation of both. This results in a racemic product.

The nature of the configuration at the *excited or critically activated* state of the molecule may be represented by (b) in Fig. 1.

The configuration (b) may be viewed as derived from (a) when two pairs of octahedral bonds, holding the chelate groups *y* and *z* respectively, rotate in opposite directions along their own plane through an angle of 45° . The molecule under this condition may be regarded to assume a distorted or twisted octahedral (?) form, with bond angles between each pair remaining, however, unchanged at 90° . When the excited molecule afterwards returns to its normal state, it may either retrace its previous steps regenerating (a), or by a further rotation through 45° in the same direction as before, produce (c) which is identical with the mirror image of (a).

The molecule is not likely to lose its regular octahedral configuration until and unless the activation energy supplied is redistributed internally and transferred specifically to the rotational and vibrational degrees of freedom of the bonds concerned. This amounts to an increase in the time interval between *pre-activation* and *critical activation* with an increased chance of deactivation. The probability factor *P* and hence the *PZ*-value will thereby be lowered, as we have found in the present case.

All evidences, therefore, indicate that inversion or racemisation of an optically active compound occurs through intramolecular rearrangements, as was first suggested by Werner, but not with the rupture of any chemical bond, even though momentary. Racemisation in the solid state also can be explained without difficulty on this basis.

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